

Using Squeeze and Excitation Attention Mechanism to Enhance the Classification Accuracy of EEG Motor Imagery Signals

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Abstract: The communication process between the human brain and the computer is an important thing these days for various reasons, as humans can now issue commands to electronic devices by reading the electrical signals of brain and translating them into programming commands that the computer understands and interprets. The Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) technology or system is considered one of the best technologies in this field, where brain signals or Electroencephalogram (EEG) motor imagery (MI) are taken as input to this system and translated into commands on the computer, scientific research in the field of artificial intelligence and machine learning, especially the so-called brain-computer interfaces, is no longer directed only to people with motor disabilities, but rather has become directed for general use in order to improve Experience our use of computers and human communication with computers better. in addition, to assist disabled people, control smart devices or environments, and even augment human capabilities. In this article, we propose a squeeze and excitation attention-based convolutional neural network, this model SE-CNN utilizes multiple techniques to boost the performance of MI classification with a relatively small number of parameters, SE attention block enhances the generalization and robustness of the network. In the BCI Competition IV-2a dataset, our proposed model has obtained good experimental results, achieving accuracies of 83.44% for subject-specific performance on the BCI-2a dataset using the same original competition division (hold-out approach: 50% training trials and 50% test trials). In addition, extensive ablative experiments and fine-tuning experiments were conducted.

Keywords: Attention Mechanism, Squeeze and Excitation (SE), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Electroencephalogram (EEG), Motor Imagery (MI), Brain-Computer Interface (BCI), Residual Connection

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Introduction

Stroke and traffic accidents are one of the main reasons why the lives of a large number of people are tragic, due to their exposure to hemiplegia or severe disability, which brings a heavy burden on the patient and his family during his health care. During the past two decades, scientific research in the field of artificial intelligence and machine learning,

especially in what is called Brain-Computer Interface (BCI), is no longer directed only to those with motor disabilities, but has also become directed for general uses. Brain-computer interface (BCI) enables direct communication between the human brain and external devices by converting and transmitting neural signals as control commands for assistive devices [1]. people gradually realize that BCI has the potential to change the world and further improve the quality of life, and its industrial applications are extensive, ranging from medical applications to human enhancement [2]. The brain signal can be recorded using various techniques, such as electroencephalography (EEG). EEG is a noninvasive method that records the electrical activities of the brain. The EEG signal is captured on the scalp as a two-dimensional (2-D) matrix of real values (time and channel). EEG is widely used and preferred over other techniques due to its ease of use, low cost, low risk, portability, and high temporal resolution, making it suitable for industrial applications [3]. Neuroscience has proven the existence of 100 billion neurons in the human brain, which are distinguished by their electrochemical properties and which can be measured and described through the forms of brain signals or wavelets. These wavelets describe various brain activities (sleep, Lethargy, movement, deep thinking and concentration etc.). Based on the amplitudes and frequencies of brain impulses shift from one state of a human to the next, such as sleep and awareness [4]. Brain Rhythms are related with five primary brain waves. These frequency bands, which have both low and high frequencies, are known as: Alpha(α), Theta(θ), Beta(β), Delta(δ) and Gamma(γ)

Fig. 1: Frequency bands associated with brain rhythms

Brain signals are among the most complex biological signals in the human body, as the process of processing and classifying them requires for accuracy and to use certain algorithms based on optimizing the initial processing of signals in order to give the best accuracy possible classification, where the signals that are electric potentials at low frequency and voltage are extracted according to the area from which the signals are taken, it can be taken from the surface of the brain or directly from the inside of the brain, Therefore, accurately identifying human intention from low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and non-stationary brain signals is currently a big challenge. Furthermore, existing many types of artifacts sources, such as biological artifacts (e.g., muscle movements, eye blinking), electronic equipment (e.g., computers and wireless devices), and environmental noise (e.g., light and sound).

Fig. 2: The different types of artifacts

Generally, we have many methods to solve these problems and improve the accuracy of classification and increase the SNR value. Researchers have proposed various preprocessing methods (filtering, data reduction algorithms like ICA, PCA etc.) and feature extraction methods, such as common spatial pattern (CSP), wavelet transform (WT) and Riemannian covariance [5]. Here, we can notice the previous ways depend on machine learning concept, that means we have an important step before classify the EEG signals and it's features extraction. So, obtaining good features is not easy and It needs more experience in how to select features and a complete understanding of brain signals and the information they carry, in addition to the cost time and effort.

Starting from here, deep learning (DL) approaches are easy to implement also the features will be extracted automatically, furthermore we can enhance the accuracy of the model better than using traditional machine learning techniques.

Recently, DL approaches have been demonstrated to be highly effective in developing EEG-based BCI [6]. In the field of BCI based on MI EEG signals, DL techniques have been used for feature extraction and classification [7]. The first famous network for analyzing EEG signals is the convolutional neural network (CNN) [8]. CNN is a multi-layer neural network that takes inspiration from the organization of the visual cortex in the brain [9]. Each convolutional layer consists of multiple convolution filters (or kernels) that are activated and trained by sliding them over the input layer. The convolutional layer has two key properties: sparse interaction and parameter sharing. Therefore, CNN can not only focus on spatial local features but also greatly reduce the number of training parameters required by the neural network. Additionally, the non-linear transformations achieved by the multi-layer structure of deep neural networks can extract some crucial low-level features. This makes the method a very suitable tool for classification and regression tasks [10]. In this study, we propose SE-CNN model for improving the accuracy of the EEG-MI signals (or trials) and in the same time to extract the most important features from EEG signals. So, the SE block is employed to weight the information from different channels. In addition, it can improve the feature information from key channels, and on the other hand, it provides a certain degree of noise suppression.

This study employs residual structures, kernel and bias regularization L2 in addition to early stopping technique to avoid or decrease the issue of overfitting in deep CNNs, while also enhancing the network's generalization capability. The proposed model achieves good results in the BCI Competition IV-2a (BCI-2a) dataset [11].

Literature Review

In this section, we will discuss some research on the analysis of EEG signals using deep learning and convolutional neural networks.

Vernon J. Lawhern et al. have proposed a model for EEG classification based on Convolutional Neural Network [12], They suggested a model called EEGNet, a compact CNN architecture for EEG-based BCIs that can be applied across several different BCI paradigms, can be trained with very limited data and can produce neurophysiologically interpretable features. The network starts with a temporal convolution to learn frequency filters, then uses a depthwise convolution, connected to each feature map individually, to learn frequency-specific spatial filters. The separable convolution is a combination of a depthwise convolution, which learns a temporal summary for each feature map individually, followed by a pointwise convolution, which learns how to optimally mix the feature maps together. Thorir Mar Ingolfsson et al. have used a new methodology to classify EEG-MI signals [13]. The network here is the same structure of the previous network (EEGNet), the output feature map of the separable convolution still contains temporal information; therefore, the addition of a temporal convolutional network (TCN) further exploits temporal information. Schirrmestern et al. have suggested a method for EEG decoding and visualization [14], they designed a deep ConvNet architecture inspired by successful architectures in computer vision, they were interested in such a generic architecture for two reasons, they aimed to uncover whether such a generic ConvNet designed only with minor expert knowledge can reach competitive accuracies, and to lend support to the idea that standard ConvNets can be used as a general-

purpose tool for brain signal decoding tasks. Yazeed K. Musallam et al. have proposed a modified method on EEG-TCNet and it called EEG-TCNet Fusion [15], They proposed an efficient TCNet-Fusion model for MI-EEG classification. Modifications to the actual TCN model are done by adding a fusion layer to build rich feature maps to improve the performance of the model and TCN is applied to extract additional temporal features. Concatenation is then applied between the output of the TCN and the EEGNet blocks to alleviate feature loss and build a rich feature map. Hamdi Altaheri et al. have proposed a new idea to improve the classification accuracy of EEG-MI signals by adding attention mechanism and sliding window (SW) technique [16], the proposed ATCNet model consists of three main blocks: convolutional (CV) block, attention (AT) block, and temporal convolutional (TC) block, CV block encodes low-level spatio-temporal information within the MI-EEG signal through three convolutional layers: temporal, channel depthwise, and spatial convolutions. The output of the CV block is a temporal sequence with a higher level representation. The AT block then highlights the most important information in the temporal sequence using a multihead self-attention (MSA). Wenlong Wang et al. they have proposed EEG-FMCNN model [17] to classify the EEG-MI signals in the BCI Competition IV-2a dataset, a fusion multi-branch 1D convolutional neural network to decode MI-EEG signals without pre-processing stage. The utilization of multi-branch 1D convolution not only exhibits a certain level of noise tolerance but also addresses the issue of inter-subject variability to some extent. This is attributed to the ability of multi-branch architectures to capture information from different frequency bands, enabling the establishment of optimal convolutional scales and depths. Furthermore, we incorporate 1D squeeze-and-excitation (SE) blocks and shortcut connections at appropriate locations to further enhance the generalization and robustness of the network.

Research Methodology

The proposed SE-CNN model consists of three main blocks: convolutional block, attention block, and temporal convolutional block. convolutional block encodes low-level spatio-temporal information within the MI-EEG signal through three convolutional layers: temporal, channel depthwise, and spatial convolutions. The output of the convolutional block is a temporal sequence with a higher level representation. The attention block then highlights the most important information in the temporal sequence using squeeze and excitation (SE) block. Finally, the temporal convolutional block extracts high-level temporal features within the temporal sequence and feeds them into a fully connected (FC) layer with a Softmax classifier to get the specific class. Fig. 3 Explains the components of the squeeze and excitation attention-based convolutional neural network model.

Fig. 3: Component of the proposed SE-CNN model

Preprocessing and Input Representation

In this paper, we feed raw MI-EEG signals into the proposed model without preprocessing, i.e., the full frequency band, all channels, and without artifact removal. SE-CNN model takes as input a motor imagery trial $X_i \in RC \times T$ consisting of

C channels (EEG electrodes) and T time points. The objective of the SE-CNN model is to map the input MI trial X_i to its corresponding class y_i , given a set of m labeled MI trials $S = \{X_i, y_i\}_{i=1}^m$, where $y_i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ is the corresponding class label for trial X_i and n is the total number of defined classes for set S. For the BCI-2a [11] dataset, $T = 1125$ time points, $C = 22$ EEG channels, $n = 4$ MI classes, and $m = 5184$ MI trials. Here in the Figure 4. We can see the scheme of each MI trial that recorded during the session.

Fig. 4: Timing scheme of the BCI IV-2a motor imagery dataset

Table.1: Details of information and parameters in the BCI Competition IV-2a

#Subjects	#Sessions	#Runs in each session	#MI trials in each run	#Total no. of trials	#Classes
9	2	6 for training and 6 for testing	48-trials (12 for each class)	288 for each session for each subject	4-classes (right hand, left hand, both feet and tongue)

Convolutional Block

The convolutional block is similar to the EEGNet architecture proposed in [12]. convolutional block differs from EEGNet by using 2-D convolution instead of separable convolution, which showed better performance. convolutional block also uses different parameter values than those used in [16]. Convolutional block consists of three convolutional layers, as shown in Figure 5. The first layer performs a temporal convolution using F1 filters of size (1, KC), where KC is the filter length in the time axis. KC was set to be one-fourth of the sampling rate (64 for BCI-2a). This allows the filters to extract temporal information associated with frequencies above 4 Hz. The output of this layer is F1 temporal feature maps. The second layer is a depthwise convolution with F2 filters of size (C, 1), where C is the number of EEG channels. Using depthwise convolution, each filter extracts spatial features (i.e., related to EEG channels) from a single temporal feature map. Therefore, the output of this layer is $F1 \times D$ feature maps, where D is the number of filters linked to each temporal feature map in the previous layer. D is set empirically to 2. $F1 \times D$ determine the output dimension of the CV block. The depthwise convolution is followed by an average pooling layer of size (1, 8) to abstract the temporal data by a factor of 8. This reduces the sampling rate of the signal to ~ 32 Hz. The third convolutional layer consists of F2 filters of size (1, KC2). KC2 was set to 16 to decode MI activities within 500 ms (for 32 Hz sampled data). Finally, a second average pooling layer with a size of (1, P2) is used to reduce the sampling rate to $\sim 32/P2$ Hz. P2 is used to control the length of the temporal sequence produced by convolutional block. The second and third convolution layers are followed by batch normalization (BN) to speed up network training and then by exponential linear unit (ELU) activation for nonlinearity. Convolutional block output a sequence $z_i \in \mathbb{R}^{T_c \times d}$ of temporal representation consisting of T_c temporal vectors each with dimension $d = F2 = F1 \times D$. We empirically set d to 32. The length of the temporal sequence z_i is determined by the following equation.1, where T refers to the time points of the original EEG signal.

$$T_c = T / 8P2 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Fig.5: The convolutional block receives a raw MI-EEG signal and outputs a temporal sequence with TC elements. Each element is a vector of size F2.

Squeeze and Excitation Block

We term the Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) block, that adaptively recalibrates channel-wise feature responses by explicitly modelling interdependencies between channels the goal of improving the quality of representations produced by a network by explicitly modelling the interdependencies between the channels of its convolutional features [18]. The SE block consists of two components: squeeze and excitation. The squeeze part addresses channel dependencies by quantifying each channel’s contribution through one-dimensional global average pooling, resulting in a corresponding real-valued number (Zc). This number has a certain level of global receptive field.

$$Z_c = Fsq(uc) = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=1}^w uc(i) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where W represents the length of data in a channel, uc is the channel feature, the excitation operation examines the dependency level between channels by using the self-gating mechanism, based on channel interdependence, which generates a weight (Sc) for each feature channel, similar to a gate. The Sc is calculated as follows:

$$Sc = Fex(Z_c, W) = \sigma(W2 \bullet \delta(W1Z_c)) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where σ and δ are sigmoid and exponential linear unit (ELU) activation functions, respectively. The first fully connected layer (dimension reduction layer), uses a restoration ratio (r) control, and in this paper, r is set to 4. W2 is the second fully connected layer (dimension expansion layer). Finally, the feature channels (uc) are multiplied with the weights (Sc) of the original channels to obtain the output of the one-dimensional block, as shown in equation. 4

$$\overline{Xc} = Fscal(uc, Sc) = ucSc \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Fig. 6: The Structure of the SE block. C denotes the number of feature maps and W denotes the size of feature maps

Temporal Convolutional Block

The temporal convolutional block has the same architecture as the TCN described in [13]. TCN consists of a stack of residual blocks. The residual block composes of two dilated causal convolutional layers, each one followed by batch normalization [19] and exponential linear unit (ELU) activation function with a depth of 2 consisting of two residual blocks, kernel size = 4, and number of filters = 32. The output of the first residual block is the input of the second. The receptive field size for this TCN will be 19, so the input length Tw should be ≤ 19. This figure shows a sequence of 16 temporal elements (Tw= 16) entering the TCN, as shown in Fig. 7.

The receptive field size (RFS) of the TCN increases exponentially with the number of stacked residual blocks L due to the exponential increase in dilation D with each succeeding block. The RFS is controlled by two parameters: the number of residual blocks L and the kernel size KT, as defined in equation.5

$$RFS = 1 + 2(KT - 1)(2^L - 1) \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Fig. 7: Visualize a TCN block

Experimental Results and Discussion

Selected Dataset and Evaluation Approaches

BCI Competition IV-2a (BCI-2a) dataset [11] is used to train and evaluate the proposed model. BCI-2a dataset consists of 5184 trials of MI-EEG data recorded using 22 EEG and 3 EOG electrodes from nine subjects (576 trials per subject). MI trials last 4 s and were sampled at 250 Hz and filtered between 0.5 and 100 Hz. Each trial belongs to one of four MI tasks: imagining of movement of the left hand (class 1), right hand (class 2), both feet (class 3), and tongue (class 4). For each subject, two sessions were recorded on different days. Each session consists of 288 trials per subject. One of these sessions is used to train the model and the other for evaluation. The number of samples in each trial is 1125, so the length of MI trial is (4.5 s * sampling rate 250 Hz), therefore the input of the convolutional layer will be a tensor (1*22*1125) for each MI trial. The proposed model is evaluated using subject-dependent (subject-specific), we used the same training and testing data as the original competition, 288*9 trials in session 1 for training, and 288*9 trials in session 2 for testing.

Performance Metrics

The proposed models in this article are evaluated using accuracy, and Kappa score

$$Acc = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n TP_i / I_i}{n} \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

Where TP_i is the true positive, i.e., the number of correctly predicted samples in class i, I_i is the number of samples in class i, and n indicates the number of classes (4-classes).

$$K_{Score} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{a=1}^n \frac{P_a - P_e}{1 - P_e} \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

Where n is the number of classes, P_a is the actual percentage of agreement, and P_e is the expected percentage chance of agreement.

Training Procedure

The model was trained and tested without GPU unit (just CPU) cori9, 13th Gen with 16 GB RAM and it took about 7 hours till finish the training and evaluation operations. The model is trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of (0.0009), batch size of (64), a categorical cross-entropy loss over (500) epochs with a patience of (300), and kernel-bias regularization l2 (0.01) and dropout (0.3). Finally, the proposed SE-CNN model achieves an overall accuracy of 83.44% and a κ-score of 0.7797.

Comparison to Recent Studies

In this section, we will present our results and compare them with some models that use the same dataset with various deep learning techniques.

Fig. 8: Training and testing accuracy for each subject

Fig. 9: Testing Accuracy Values per Subject

Fig. 10: The confusion matrix for each subject

Here, we have the confusion matrix for the all subjects (whole model), from this matrix we can calculate some evaluation metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, support and f1-score etc.

Fig. 11: Confusion matrix for all subjects (average accuracy for the whole SE-CNN model)

We can analysis our model by compare the accuracy and loss function error during training and testing stages and notice the difference. Of course during training phase the accuracy will be better and it may reach 100% on the contrary during the testing or evaluation phase the accuracy will be decreased because the model has new data to recognize. The most problems that the deep learning faces, that is related to over-fitting and under-fitting so we should solve these two problems to make balance between variance and bias (trade-off variance and bias). We used some techniques to avoid or alleviate over-fitting problem, such as weight decay (kernel and bias regularization l2), dropout neurons, early stopping epochs. Figure 12. Shows the loss function error for each subject as following:

Fig. 12: Loss Function Error for each Subject during Training and Testing

Fig. 13: Loss Function Error per Subject

Here we will review in Table 2. a comparison in terms of accuracy and k-score between some models and the proposed model (SE-CNN).

Table. 2: Performance (Accuracy (%) and K-score) Comparison of Subject-specific Classification Using BCI-2a Dataset for the Proposed Model with Other Reproduced Models

Model	Proposed SE-CNN		Incep-EEGNet [20]		EEGNet [12]		TCNet [13]		TCNet-Fusion [15]		DeepConvNet [8]	
Year	2023		2020		2017		2020		2021		2017	
Subject	Acc.	k	Acc.	k	Acc.	k	Acc.	k	Acc.	k	Acc.	k
1	83.33	0.777	84.72	0.796	83.68	0.783	79.51	0.727	82.64	0.768	75.35	0.671
2	68.75	0.583	54.86	0.398	60.42	0.472	62.51	0.501	62.85	0.505	59.03	0.453

3	94.10	0.921	86.81	0.824	89.93	0.866	89.24	0.857	90.62	0.875	79.17	0.722
4	78.47	0.713	70.83	0.611	63.54	0.514	66.32	0.551	67.36	0.565	78.47	0.713
5	82.99	0.773	44.42	0.256	69.11	0.588	75.69	0.676	76.04	0.681	71.88	0.625
6	74.65	0.662	54.86	0.398	57.64	0.435	61.11	0.481	64.24	0.523	59.03	0.453
7	93.40	0.912	92.71	0.903	85.42	0.806	84.72	0.796	87.15	0.829	79.51	0.726
8	86.11	0.814	87.85	0.838	84.03	0.787	79.86	0.732	82.29	0.764	76.74	0.689
9	89.24	0.856	82.64	0.769	80.56	0.741	82.99	0.773	82.64	0.769	74.65	0.662
Average	83.44	0.779	73.31	0.644	74.93	0.666	75.77	0.677	77.31	0.698	72.65	0.635

Conclusion and future work

In this article, we proposed the SE-CNN model to classify motor brain signals through the use of convolutional neural networks and attention mechanism (Squeeze and Excitation) that focus on specific information from the signal. After training the model, we found that it gave good accuracy compared to other models that rely on the same method and the dataset in Classification of brain signals (EEG-MI). This paper proposes a novel EEG-based MI classification network, SE-CNN. It consists of three main blocks: the 2D convolution block encodes low-level spatio-temporal information within the MI-EEG signal through three convolutional layers: temporal, channel depthwise, and spatial convolutions. The output of the 2D convolution block is a temporal sequence with a higher level representation, the SE block assigns different weights to different channels to highlight the contributions of important channels. the temporal convolutional block extracts high-level temporal features within the temporal sequence using TCN and feeds them into a fully connected (FC) layer with a Softmax classifier. This paper conducts extensive ablation experiments. Each block in the SE-CNN model contributes significantly to the performance of the model. The experiment was conducted without any artifact removal and with a highly challenging dataset, demonstrating the model's powerful feature extraction capability for MI EEG signals

In the future, it is possible to improve the model and use other types of attention mechanisms, such as multihead self-attention (MSA) and convolutional block attention module (CBAM), in addition to the process of data augmentation (DA) and preprocessing operations such as filtering, enhance the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), and data reduction principal component analysis (PCA) and independent component analysis (ICA) for removing the artifacts of EEG signals etc. All of this leads to improving the model and increasing classification accuracy.

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